

THE EFFECTS OF CORPORATE PHILOSOPHY ON NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS WITHIN THE SCOPE OF MEMBER ATTRACTION: THE EXAMPLE OF İZMİR AND MANİSA PROVINCES

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Abstract

In this study, it is aimed to determine the perceptions of members (manager and non-manager) within the scope of the basic factors of corporate philosophy in terms of member acquisition in non-governmental organizations. The survey form prepared in this context was conducted on 238 non-governmental organization members (177 managers and 51 regular members) among 83 non-governmental organizations in İzmir and Manisa provinces between March 2022 and April 2022. It has been determined that the corporate philosophy in non-governmental organizations will greatly affect member acquisition in terms of each of the "strategic dimension, orientation, internal stakeholder and teamwork, integrity and external stakeholder" factors. It has been determined that there is a moderate to moderate positive linear relationship between each factor. It is always and generally seen that the corporate philosophy affects the quality of activity, supports participatory democracy and is complied with in all processes; It has also been determined that it is always and generally seen that NGOs give sufficient importance to the corporate philosophy, but it is not seen at a rate close to 30%.

Keywords: NGO, Corporate Philosophy, Members Gain.

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1. Introduction

The main point that today's Non – governmental organizations (NGOs) focus on in all activities in the establishment, post-establishment and development stages can be expressed as the corporate philosophy. Within the scope of their corporate philosophy, NGOs tend to acquire members within the framework of their mission, vision, values and principles. In other words, it can be stated that individuals in NGOs as managers or regular members try to perform their voluntary activities in accordance with the corporate philosophy.

In this context, it can be said that NGOs are in a position to examine the main factors that affect the importance of member acquisition within the framework of their institutional philosophies. An NGO's determination of various factors in managerial processes can be explained by their caring about strategic, leadership, communication, teamwork, financial issues, openness and transparency.

In this context, the aim of this study is to determine the perceptions of members (manager and non-manager) in terms of the main factors regarding the effect of corporate philosophy on membership acquisition in NGOs. The prepared questionnaire was applied to 238 NGO members (177 managers and 51 regular members) within the scope of 83 NGOs in İzmir and Manisa provinces between March 2022 and April 2022.

2. Conceptual Framework

2.1. Non-Governmental Organizations

The European Economic and Social Committee (ESC) defines NGOs as “all organizational structures that assume responsibility for the benefit of society and act as an intermediary between public authorities and citizens” (Güder, 2005: 10). In more concrete terms, in terms of legal personality, NGOs are associations, foundations, unions, chambers, etc.(Antalya, 2000: 14).

In this context, NGOs can provide numerous benefits to the society in a democratic framework within the scope of projects with modest resources by emphasizing voluntarism. (Yildirim, 2004: 218).

As stakeholders, NGOs play an important role in protecting and developing interests in the public sphere, integrating the society and ensuring democratic participation (Dogan, 2002: 244). Similarly, media, society in general, other NGOs and donor relations can also be integrated into the processes (Balser and McClusky, 2005: 295). In this context, ideally NGOs are requested to observe transparency, accountability and equal opportunity (Tekeli, 2002: 21).

On the other hand, NGOs can also include the nature of forming a pressure group in today's societies that differ in various aspects (economic development, culture, interests, etc.) (Yücekök, 1998: 2).

NGO members, on the other hand, can take part in NGOs within a framework that includes personal reasons within the scope of socialization and establishing a good environment, apart from general reasons such as helping, problem solving, meeting with the society, and contributing to the establishment of justice within the scope of volunteering (Yanay and Yanay, 2008: 66).

3. The Concept of Corporate Philosophy in NGOs

In an organization, corporate philosophy can be expressed as mission, vision, values and principles (Akyürek, 2005: 43).

Mission is generally defined in three different frameworks in the literature. It is defined in terms of organizations, in terms of moral and ethical values, and finally in terms of military (Murphy, 1998: 29).

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Mission is what an organization is for when it is in. From a strategic point of view, it is more and more inclusive (Miller, 2003: 138-153, Hultman, 2005: 39). NGOs should take care to determine their missions in a way that will be beneficial to the society, the individual and the environment (Piercy, N., Morgan, N. 1994: 7). If an NGO cannot clearly explain why it exists, it will be impossible to distinguish between its existence or not. (Yaman, 2005: 12).

Vision; It is an abstract goal of what an organization wants to be in the future (Özmutaf, 2011: 152, Kolk, 2003: 283). The features that need attention for the mission should also be considered for the vision.

Mission and vision are both processes taken together. While being determined, it should be applicable and be implemented (McDonald, 2007: 259).

Values and principles are the important elements that are taken into consideration in determining the mission and vision. While determining these two issues, which are especially important for non-governmental organizations, the aims and priorities of non-governmental organizations are taken into account.

Value is the moral and abstract hopes held within an organization (Kolk, 2003: 281). The values that each non-governmental organization will have may be different. These values may vary according to the reason and aims of the non-governmental organization. In this context, NGOs are also called value-oriented organizations (Lewis, 2000: 166).

Principles, on the other hand, can be defined as the rules and functioning of the determined mission and vision in line with the values possessed by the organization and the rules applied (Courtney, 2002: 38). NGOs, unlike other organizations, may be broader and more diverse in their application of principles. This situation shows existence in principles as well as values.

Institutional philosophy, mission, vision, values and principles will be formed as a whole, and can emerge in a healthy way.

4. Corporate Philosophy and Member Acquisition in NGOs

In the literature, it is emphasized that the strategic dimension is becoming increasingly important for NGOs and that the strategic dimension should be supported within the scope of mission, vision, value, principles, objectives, analyzes (internal and external environment, stakeholder), managerial processes, performance indicators and key areas (Courtney, 2001: 113). Therefore, it is important for NGOs to develop management and communication tools between the organization and its member / potential members in member acquisition. In this context, both classical methods and tools and the internet can be used (Hart, 2005: 139).

In this context, non-governmental organizations may need a large number of volunteers in order to realize their projects in line with their goals and objectives (Güder, 2005: 152). It can be stated that the corporate philosophy is important for it to be voluntary gain. In this context, taking the opinions of the members will also increase the efficiency of the processes (Barbeito, 2004: 11).

If the mission, vision, values and principles included in the corporate philosophy are adopted by a large audience, volunteer and member acquisition will be shaped accordingly. In this study, the effect of corporate philosophy on member acquisition is discussed.

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5. Method

5.1. Purpose of the research

The main purpose of the research is to determine the perceptions of members (manager and non-manager) regarding the effect of corporate philosophy on membership acquisition in NGOs.

6. Data

The questionnaire form prepared (for the research consists of three main parts. In the first part, the independent variables of the research are age, gender, educational status, type of NGO, field of duty in the NGO (president, vice-president, secretary, other) and the experience period in the NGO. In the second part, questions about the effect of corporate philosophy on the quality of activity, the support of participatory democracy of the corporate philosophy, the compliance with the corporate philosophy in all processes and the situation of NGOs giving sufficient importance to the corporate philosophy were included in the second part. In the third part, there are 25 propositions that are predicted to affect the membership of the NGO within the framework of certain dimensions of the corporate philosophy. For statistical evaluations, the propositions were given a weight value of 1 for strongly disagree, 2 for strongly disagree, 3 for moderately agreeing, 4 for agree, 5 for strongly agree, within the scope of 5-point Likert scale for statistical evaluations. The 25 propositions were gathered under five factors as a result of factor analysis.

7. Analyzes

The survey form prepared for the research was applied between March 2022 and April 2022 by face-to-face survey method within the framework of NGOs in the provinces of İzmir and Manisa. In reaching out to NGOs, the web pages containing the guide for NGOs published by the Turkish History Foundation in 2005 and the city guide for the provinces of İzmir and Manisa were used. The aforementioned publication of the Turkish History Foundation contains information about 430 NGOs in the Izmir and Manisa provinces section (Civil Society Organizations Guide, 2005, pp.620-622; Kent News; Izmir Metropolitan Municipality; Izmir Union of Chambers of Craftsmen and Craftsmen, 15 /December/2015). It was applied to 238 NGO members (manager and non-manager) within the scope of a total of 83 NGOs. SPSS software was used within the scope of statistical analysis in the research. Within the scope of the research, factor analysis, population mean t test and correlation analysis were performed.

8. Theoretical Model of the Research

The theoretical model of the research is based on the assumption that the corporate philosophy of NGOs will affect member acquisition in terms of various factors (See Figure 1). In this framework, the effect of its relation with the factors that are thought to affect the corporate philosophy of the NGOs on the acquisition of members to the NGO was determined.

Figure 1. Theoretical Model of the Research

9. Research Hypotheses

H₁: In NGOs, corporate philosophy has an impact on member acquisition in terms of ... factor (Strategic dimension, direction, internal stakeholder and teamwork, holistic dimension, external stakeholder dimension)

H₂: Among the factors emerging within the scope of corporate philosophy in NGOs, positive there is a linear relationship / co-change in the direction.

10. Findings

10.1. Findings in the Scope of Socio-Demographic and Institutional Philosophy

The mean and standard deviation of the general age (min-max=18-75) of the respondents (n= 238) was 37.4±12.15. The mean age and standard deviation of the surveyed women (n=77, 33.8%) was 32.9±10.44, and the mean age and standard deviation of the men (n=151, 66.2%) was 38.7±12.38' is 1.8% (n=5) of the respondents were primary, 9.3% were secondary (n=23), 16.8% were high school (n=43), and the majority 72.1% were university students. (n=167) graduated. 43.7% of the participants are in the association (n=104), 46.6% in the foundation (n=111) and 9.7% in the other (n=23) NGO structuring. Of the participants, 36.9% were president (n=88), 32% were vice presidents (n=75), 10.1%

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were secretary (n=24), and 21.5% were regular members (n= 51) is. On the other hand, the majority of the participants (n=173, 72.7%) within the scope of NGOs have less than 10 years of experience, while nearly a quarter of them (n=65, 27.3%) have 10 or more years of experience. Table 1 shows the perceptions of NGO members on some general issues within the scope of corporate philosophy. In this context, more than half of the NGO members stated that the corporate philosophy always affects the quality of their activities, and about a quarter of them stated that it usually does. About 48% of the participants emphasize that the corporate philosophy always supports participatory democracy, and about 20% of them generally supports it. It has been determined that 37.6% of the respondents always and 26.1% of them generally respond to the compliance with the corporate philosophy in all processes. In NGOs, 31.2% of those who always agree to give sufficient importance to the corporate philosophy, 27.4% generally agree, and 27.2% never agree. In this context, it can be expressed that CSOs are insufficient in complying with the corporate philosophy in all processes and that sufficient importance is not given (Table 1).

Table 1. General Topics Regarding Corporate Philosophy

Scale	Corporate Philosophy Affects Operation Quality		Corporate Philosophy Supports Participatory Democracy		Corporate Philosophy is Complied with in All Processes		NGOs Give Sufficient Importance to Corporate Philosophy	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Always	125	52,6	113	47,5	90	37,6	74	31,2
Usually	46	19,2	41	17,4	62	26,1	65	27,4
Sometimes	25	10,7	31	12,9	37	15,7	34	14,2
Never	42	17,5	53	22,2	49	20,6	65	27,2
Total	238	100	238	100	127	100	238	100

10.2. Reliability of the Measurement Tool

Factor analysis was applied to 25 propositions in the third part of the questionnaire within the scope of principal component analysis. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin value is 0.887. As a result of the Bartlett Test of Sphericity, the null hypothesis (H0: correlation matrix is the unit matrix) was rejected (=2770,987, p=0.000). The diagonal values of the anti-image correlation matrix vary between 0.952 and 0.834. Within the scope of these three results, the structure consisting of 25 propositions was found to be suitable for factor analysis (Table 2). As a result of factor analysis, 5 factors were formed. Five factors explain the total variance at the rate of 76,539%. Total variance; the first factor explained 25.451%, the second factor 14.772%, the third factor 13.485%, the fourth factor 11'296% and the fifth factor 10.423%. Within the framework of these results, it was determined that the factors pointed out by the propositions in the questionnaire explained the subject to a high degree. The Cronbach Alpha value is 0.951. Therefore, the five-factor (25-proposition) structure has very high reliability. In addition, Cronbach's Alpha values show consistency on the basis of factors and items (Table 2). The overall question mean (item-means) for 25 propositions is 4.2 and the mean variance is 0.05. When the factors are examined;

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It is seen that the F1 factor includes the strategic dimension, the f2 factor includes orientation, the f3 factor includes internal stakeholder and team work, the f4 factor includes integrity, and the f5 factor includes the external stakeholder dimension (Table 2).

Table 2. Factor Loads and Confidence Coefficients

Corporate philosophy (mission, vision, values, principles) ... positively affects member acquisition	Factor					Cronbach Alfa Score	
	f1	f2	f3	f4	f5	General=0,951	
Being effective in identifying opportunities and threats in the external environment	,853	,197	,151	,141	,144	,932	,934
Being effective in determining our strengths and weaknesses	,814	,311	,023	,071	,121	,936	
Ownership by top management	,794	,219	,152	,239	,083	,934	
Being compatible with the strategies (the ways that achieve the goals and objectives)	,777	,307	,065	,214	,124	,936	
Ownership by members	,771	,149	,362	,106	,103	,935	
Compliance with NGO goals and objectives	,737	,325	,021	,228	,162	,938	
Be clear, concise, and understandable	,725	-,030	,348	,214	,062	,942	
Integration with volunteering activities	,617	,128	,384	,380	,096	,940	,912
Being a development	,213	,798	,315	,115	,135	,877	
Compatibility with educational processes	,284	,767	,296	,141	,146	,868	
Be motivating	,349	,761	,076	,200	,143	,873	
Being an innovation provider	,169	,687	,505	,155	,118	,898	
Leadership is inclusive	,441	,582	-,024	,462	,102	,905	,878
Making teamwork successful	,221	,124	,807	,079	,150	,810	
Satisfying its members	,180	,348	,768	,097	,004	,813	
Its members are developers	,201	,487	,734	,032	,062	,828	
Encouraging teamwork	,155	,022	,671	,258	,458	,858	,909
Integration with management processes	,421	,237	,130	,763	,079	,827	
Integration with NGO image	,330	,281	,167	,756	,076	,910	
Integration with communication activities	,512	,146	,195	,674	,129	,874	,782
Being accepted by the stakeholders (businesses, state institutions, etc.)	,061	,094	,082	,387	,741	,609	
Providing transparency and reliability in financial matters	,200	,244	,105	,159	,722	,611	
Being supported by the media	,348	,277	,093	-,039	,679	,612	
Acceptable by the target audience	,025	,006	,384	,436	,609	,638	
Being able to be expressed with information technologies	,011	-,032	,020	-,277	,552	,645	

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Table 2 (cont'd)

Corporate philosophy (mission, vision, values, principles) ... positively affects member acquisition	Factor					Cronbach Alfa Score	
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Being effective in determining our strengths and weaknesses	,814	,311	,023	,071	,121	,936	
Ownership by top management	,794	,219	,152	,239	,083	,934	
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Ownership by members	,771	,149	,362	,106	,103	,935	
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Being able to be expressed with information technologies	,011	-,032	,020	- ,277	,552	,645	

10.3. Findings Regarding Factors

H1 hypothesis was accepted for all five factors (Table 3). Therefore, it has been revealed within the scope of the perceptions of the NGO members participating in the survey that the corporate philosophy of the NGOs will have a high impact on member acquisition in terms of strategic dimension, orientation, internal stakeholder and teamwork, holism and each of the shower stakeholder factors.

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Table 3. One-Sample t-Test on the Basis of Factors

Factor	N	$\bar{x} \pm s$	Single Sample t test (Test Value $3 \leq \mu$)	
			t	P
f1 (Strategic Dimension)	238	4,1±,92	13,765	,000
f2 (Direction)	238	4,0±,92	12,892	,000
f3 (Internal stakeholder and teamwork)	238	4,0±,96	11,751	,000
f4 (Integrity)	238	4,1±,97	12,879	,000
f5 (External stakeholder)	238	4,1±,86	15,264	,000

The H2 hypothesis was accepted within the scope of the correlations of the five factors with each other (Table 4). In this context, there is a moderately positive linear relationship / co-change between the "strategic dimension" factor and the "management", "internal stakeholder and teamwork" and "integrity" factors. There is a moderately positive linear relationship / co-change between the "direction factor" and the factors of internal stakeholder and team work" and "integrity". There is a positive linear relationship/covariance close to medium level between the "external stakeholder" factor and the "strategic dimension" factor, the "leading" factor and the "integrity" factor (Table 4).

Table 4. Correlation Between Factors

Factor		f1	f2	f3	f4
f2 (Direction)	r	,657**			
	p	,000			
f3 (Internal stakeholder and teamwork)	r	,533**	,622**		
	p	,000	,000		
f4 (Integrity)	r	,684**	,612**	,451**	
	p	,000	,000	,000	
f5 (External stakeholder)	r	,382**	,405**	,421**	,372**
	p	,000	,000	,000	,000

**. Correlation significance level 0.01 and n=238.

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11. Discussion and Conclusion

Since NGOs are non-profit organizations that act with the logic of volunteers, they can be considered as organizations that basically have to protect their corporate philosophies. In this framework, NGOs will be able to maximize their member acquisition performance by determining, owning and developing their missions, visions, values and principles in a participatory manner.

However, putting the corporate philosophy into practice in all managerial processes and activities of NGOs will only be possible if they consider certain factors. In this context, the factors mentioned within the scope of the research were determined in five basic dimensions as "strategic dimension, orientation, internal stakeholder and teamwork, holism and external stakeholder".

Indeed, the integration of corporate philosophy with an appropriate strategic plan; giving importance to leadership, education, motivation, innovation and development in the orientation phase; giving importance to the satisfaction and development of internal stakeholders and teamwork; implementing and supporting management processes, communication activities and NGO image with a holistic perspective; Giving importance to target audiences, businesses, state institutions, other NGOs, media relations within the scope of external stakeholders, and ensuring transparency and reliability in financial matters will ensure the implementation of the corporate philosophy and enable the NGO to approach member acquisition positively.

On the other hand, it can be stated as supporting the view that the positive relationship between the five factors mentioned above will affect the member acquisition with a more positive synergy. Therefore, according to the results of the research, it can be said that the corporate philosophy will maximize the effect of member acquisition together with the five factors mentioned.

As a result of the research, the following inferences and ideas can be put forward:

- i. Institutional philosophy in NGOs is directly related to managerial factors in member acquisition,
- ii. The study revealed a scientific approach to NGOs in terms of management organization,
- iii. Since this study was conducted in the metropolitan cities of İzmir and Manisa, it can be stated that the results are highly representative of Turkey.

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Çatışma Beyanı (Competing interests)

Çalışmanın yazarı, herhangi bir çıkar çatışması olmadığını beyan etmektedir.

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

References

- Akyürek, R. (2005). Kurumsal İletişimde Stratejik Yönetim ve Planlama, Anadolu Univ. Yayınları: Eskişehir. S:43
- Antalya, G. (2000), “Tüzel Kişilikler ve Bunun İçinde Gönüllü Kuruluşlar”, STK’lar ve Yasalar, Etik, Deprem, STK Sempozyumları, Türkiye Ekonomik ve Toplumsal Tarih Vakfı Yay., İstanbul.
- Balsler, D. Ve McClusky, J. (2005) Managing Stakeholder Relationship and Nonprofit Organization Effectiveness, *Nonprofit Management & Leadership*, 15(3): 295-315.
- Barbeito, C.L. (2004) Human Resource Policies and Procedures for Nonprofit Organizations, John Willey and Sons, Hoboken, USA.
- Courtney, R. (2001), Strategic Management for Voluntary Nonprofit Organizations, Florence, USA.
- Courtney, R. (2002). Strategic Management For Voluntary Nonprofit Organizations. Taylor Francis Group Boks Ltd.: New York.
- Doğan, İ. (2002), Sivil Toplum, Alfa Yay., İstanbul.
- Güder, N. (2005) *Sivil Toplumcunun El Kitabı*, STGP Yay., Ankara.
- Hart, T. (2005) Nonprofit Internet Strategies: Best Practices for Marketing, Communications, and Fundraising Success, John Wiley and Sons, Hoboken, USA.
- Hultman, K. (2005), Evaluating Organization Values, *Organizational Development Journal*, 23(4), 32-44
- Kolk A. (2003) "Trends in Sustainability Reporting by the Fortune Global 250" *Business Strategy and the Environment* 12(5) September-October (279-291)
- Lewis, D. (2000), Management og Non-Governmental Organizations: Catalysis, Partner and Implementors, Florence, USA.
- McDonald, R. E. (2007). An Investigation of Innovation in Nonprofit Organizations: The Role of Organizational Mission. *Nonprofit and Voluntary. Sector Quarterly* 36(2): 257, 260.
- Miller, P. (2003), Organisation Values and Generational Values: A Cross Cultural Study. *Australian Journal of Business & Social Inquiry*, 1(3), 138-153.
- Murphy, J. J. (1998), The Concepts of Vision & Mission Revisited, *SBL Research Review*, 2 (1), 27-33
- Özmutaf, N.M. (2011). Sivil Toplum Kuruluşlarında Kurum Felsefesi ve Gönüllü Takımların Yönetmel Nitelikleri: Yönetici ve Üye Perspektifi, *Anadolu Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*
- Piercy, N., Morgan, N. (1994). Mission Analysis: An Operational Approach, *Journal of General Management* 19(3), 1-19.
- Tekeli, İ. (2002) “STK’lar Alanının Ahlakı, STK’lar Yerelleşme ve Yerel Yönetimler”, Türkiye Ekonomik ve Toplumsal Tarih Vakfı Yay., İstanbul: 5-28.
- Yaman, Y. (2005) “Bir STK Kurma ve İşletme”, STK’lar İçin Yönetim Rehberi, Kaknüs Yay., İstanbul.
- Yanay, V. G. ve Yanay, N. (2008) “The Decline of Motivation? From Commitment To Dropping Out Of Volunteering”, *Nonprofit Management & Leadership*, 9(1): 68-75.
- Yıldırım, İ. (2004) *Demokrasi, Sivil Toplum Kuruluşları ve Yönetişim*, Seçkin Yay., Ankara.
- Yücekök, A. (1998) “19. Yüzyıl Osmanlı Toplumundan Günümüz Türkiye’sine STK’lar ve Siyaset Sosyolojisi İlişkileri, Tanzimattan Günümüze İstanbul’da STK’lar”, Türkiye Ekonomik ve Toplumsal Tarih Vakfı Yay., İstanbul: 1-12.